
Review

Language of Instruction in the Educational Systems: A Scoping Review of Empirical Studies in the Maghreb Region

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Abstract: This scoping review examines empirical research on the language of instruction within the Maghreb region, encompassing Morocco, Algeria, Mauritania, Libya, and Tunisia. The unique linguistic landscape of the Maghreb, characterized by a mix of languages due to historical and sociopolitical influences, offers a compelling context for exploring the situation of the educational language. This study aims to examine the existing research in this area, addressing key questions regarding research contexts, focal problems, participant demographics, methodologies, outcomes, and recommendations. The methodology encompassed a four-phase, systematic approach beginning with an exhaustive search across academic databases, using a query string tailored to language instruction in Northwest Africa. This search, focusing solely on empirical studies in journal articles and excluding non-empirical sources, resulted in 352 articles. Through rigorous screening 21 articles were initially selected. A subsequent citation check added 12 more studies, while a targeted manual search in 22 selected journals known for their focus on language subjects added another 6 articles. This comprehensive and methodical process ultimately assembled a collection of 39 pertinent articles, laying a strong foundation for the scoping review by ensuring a wide-ranging examination of language instruction research within the Maghreb region. The findings provide a comprehensive overview of language instruction research in the Maghreb region, spotlighting Morocco with 27 studies across educational levels, yet revealing gaps in primary education and less focus on countries like Tunisia, Libya, and Mauritania. Research has predominantly explored secondary and higher education, delving into language use, teacher and student experiences, and the impact of language policies, with a notable lean towards qualitative methodologies. The study's findings underscore the challenges of using English as a language of instruction, highlight the crucial need for teacher training in multilingual settings, and advocate for the incorporation of local languages to embrace the region's linguistic diversity. Simultaneously, it identifies a pressing need for future research to tackle the underrepresentation of primary education in specific Maghreb countries. Additionally, it calls for the integration of quantitative methods to broaden the generalizability of findings.

Keywords: Language of Instruction, Bilingual Education, Maghreb, Multilingualism, Language in Education

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Accepted: 10 April, 2024; **Published:** 19 April, 2024

How to cite this article: Azziz Bichoualne, Yu Rong (2024). *Language of Instruction in the Educational Systems: A Scoping Review of Empirical Studies in the Maghreb Region*. *North American Academic Research*, 7(4), 34-51. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10994181>

Conflicts of Interest: There are no conflicts to declare.

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Introduction

The Maghreb region, encompassing Morocco, Algeria, Mauritania, Libya, and Tunisia, presents a complex and dynamic linguistic landscape. Historically influenced by the Arabic Islamic conquests in the 8th and 9th centuries and later by European colonization, these countries have experienced significant sociolinguistic shifts. The indigenous Berber languages, also known as Amazigh languages, have coexisted with Arabic, introduced during the Islamic conquests, and European languages like French, Italian, and Spanish brought by colonizers in the 19th century. Post-independence, efforts to assert national identity led to policies of Arabization, making Arabic the sole official language, yet French retained its dominance in many public life sectors (Zakharia, 2016). In the context of education, these countries have grappled with bilingual or multilingual policies, often reflecting broader socio-political dynamics. In Morocco, the language policy in education has been characterized by fluctuation and vagueness, reflecting the sociopolitical context and the country's linguistic diversity. The Moroccan education system is marked by partial Arabization and Arabic-French bilingualism, with French continuing to dominate in vital sectors despite Arabization efforts. This situation has led to a crisis in education, with the educational infrastructure struggling to keep up with these policies (Ennaji, 2005; Abdeljaoued, 2023). Tunisia's education system follows a similar bilingual structure, starting with Arabic and introducing French and later English. Despite sustained Arabization efforts, French remains the language of instruction in many secondary school subjects and vocational training, reflecting a continuing competition of ideologies between Arabic and French. The Tunisian language policy has been marked by inconsistencies and a general lack of enthusiasm for complete Arabization, with a preference for French in many education and administration sectors (Daoud, 2011; Roux, 2017). In Algeria, language policy in education has undergone various phases, reflecting the country's complex historical, political, and sociocultural context. The post-colonial period saw a push for Arabization, replacing French with Arabic in education. However, this monolingual vision clashed with the linguistic diversity of Algeria, leading to the maintenance of French and other languages. Today, subjects are taught in Arabic apart from foreign languages, including French and English, with recent policies being less assertive in Arabization (Zakharia, 2016; Roux, 2017). The persistence of French and the growing influence of English, alongside the official promotion of Arabic, showcase the ongoing linguistic negotiations and adjustments within the region's educational landscape (Zakharia, 2016; Abdeljaoued, 2023).

According to Van Pinxteren (2023), the language of instruction encompasses the language used for oral teaching and extends to the language in teaching materials, assessments, and exams. This broad definition incorporates various forms of language use in educational settings, ranging from dialects and code-switching to translanguaging and in-class translation. Macaro et al. (2017) explicate that the language of instruction plays a crucial role in shaping the educational experience, particularly in situations where the language of instruction is different from the student's native language, as it significantly impacts both the understanding of the subject matter and students' language proficiency. Similarly, in countries where English is not the majority's native tongue, English as a medium of instruction (EMI) refers to the utilization of the English language to instruct academic subjects. While emphasizing English for teaching academic subjects, the definition does not imply its exclusivity in the educational context. However, there is an ongoing debate about the role of English in these settings, particularly concerning whether this definition might be too narrow, especially regarding its applicability in Anglophone contexts (Macaro, 2022; Rose et al., 2021).

In light of the intricate and multifaceted nature of language instruction in the Maghreb region, where countries exhibit notable similarities in their linguistic approaches, this review aims to systematically explore and delineate the scope of research conducted in this field. To achieve a comprehensive understanding, our objective is to address the following key questions:

- In what contexts has research been carried out?
- On which research problems have researchers concentrated their efforts?
- Which participants have been incorporated in the studies?

- Which research methodologies have been utilized by researchers?
- What are the reported outcomes and recommendations?

Methodology

In order to gather extensive empirical data on the language of instruction in the Maghreb region, we have employed a scoping review. The primary purposes of doing a scoping review are to thoroughly evaluate the extent, range, and attributes of the current material and identify any deficiencies in the literature (Mak & Thomas, 2022). Scoping reviews and systematic reviews have separate goals and approaches when it comes to synthesizing evidence. In general, systematic reviews can be described as a sort of research synthesis carried out with the aim to find and collect broad evidence that is pertinent to issues (Munn et al., 2018). Systematic reviews employ a meticulous and organized methodology to collect, evaluate, and integrate information to address specific research inquiries by a rigorous methodology to minimize bias, ensuring the reliability and validity of the findings. In contrast, scoping reviews, a more recent development, aim to examine and chart the existing literature, which is particularly valuable in emerging or new research fields (Sargeant & O'Connor, 2020).

This scoping review adheres to specific inclusion criteria to ensure a focused and relevant examination of the language of instruction in the Northwest African (Maghreb) region. Eligible data sources include journal articles presenting empirical studies without language restrictions to encompass a comprehensive range of research. The geographical scope is confined to the Maghreb region of Northwest Africa, aligning the review with this area's linguistic and cultural contexts. Only studies with full-text availability are considered, facilitating in-depth analysis of the findings. Excluded from this review are sources other than journal articles. This review excludes various non-empirical sources, including theses, book chapters, policy analysis papers, conference proceedings, and similar literature. The reason for this exclusion is to focus solely on research that provides empirical evidence through the detailed examination of language instruction. The review aims to establish a solid, evidence-based comprehension of the topic, ensuring that the conclusions drawn are grounded in rigorously gathered and analyzed data.

In our scoping review, the data collection procedure was meticulously structured into four phases following establishing inclusion criteria. In the initial phase, we accessed and extracted data from seven academic databases: EBSCO, ERIC, PROQUEST, SCOPUS, WEB OF SCIENCE, and WILEY. Our approach involved a carefully designed query string, encompassing terms like "language of teaching," "multilingual education," "bilingual education," and various other phrases pertinent to the study's focus on language in education, combined with geographic identifiers relevant to Northwest Africa such as "Northwest Africa*," "North Africa*," "Algeria*," "Tunisia*," "Morocco*," "Libya*," and "Mauritania*." The second phase broadened our data collection scope, involving extracting the first 200 results from Google Scholar, allowing for a more in-depth analysis of relevant literature. This comprehensive search across databases and Google Scholar cumulatively yielded 352 articles. The data collection involved a meticulous screening process. Each article was evaluated through abstract and title screening based on the pre-defined inclusion and exclusion criteria. Two reviewers carried out this task independently, ensuring a robust and unbiased data analysis. The results from each reviewer were then compared and discussed, mainly focusing on the insights and discrepancies that emerged from the articles identified. This rigorous, multi-phased approach ensured a thorough collection and screening of data pertinent to our scoping review. By eliminating 58 items deemed duplicates, the list of prospective articles was reduced to 294. Subsequently, we thoroughly examined these publications, and after eliminating the articles outside the scope of this review, we identified a total of 21 pertinent articles that satisfied the inclusion requirements.

The third phase involved a citation check using Google Scholar for all the articles from the first and second phases. We scrutinized the articles citing the initially included articles, applying the same inclusion and exclusion criteria. This phase contributed an additional 12 articles that met the inclusion criteria.

We conducted manual searches across 22 carefully selected journals in the fourth and final phase. These journals were chosen based on three criteria: their focus on language subjects, high citation numbers, and their frequent appearance in the articles included in the previous phases. This thorough search added 6 more articles to our corpus.

The combination of these four stages resulted in a strong and thorough compilation of 39 articles that satisfied all of our criteria for inclusion. This serves as a solid basis for our scoping study. Utilizing a multifaceted strategy guaranteed a comprehensive examination and retrieval of pertinent material, which was crucial for the extensive scope and thoroughness of this study.

Fig.1: Search Strategy

Results

Research Question 1: In what contexts has research been carried out?

The research context for this scoping review constitutes a framework encompassing both geographical and educational dimensions, primarily focusing on countries in the Maghreb region. The geographical context included a range of countries: Tunisia, Morocco, Various Countries (that include Maghreb region countries in their study focus), Algeria, Libya, and Mauritania. The scoping review included 39 studies distributed across various educational levels, with 3 in Primary Education, 12 in Secondary Education, 20 in Higher Education, and 4 that included both Higher and Secondary Education.

In Tunisia, the research focuses on secondary and higher education, with one study each in these sectors, summing up to two studies. Conversely, Morocco emerges as the most researched country in this review, with a total of 27 studies. The focus in Morocco is extensively spread across primary, secondary, and higher education, with a notable emphasis on secondary (10 studies) and higher education (12 studies). Additionally, four studies in Morocco encompass both secondary and higher educational contexts.

Studies that include various countries, with a specific focus on the Maghreb region, amount to two, with a single study in primary education and one in higher education. Algeria has research predominantly in higher education, with four studies dedicated to this sector. Libya, like Tunisia, also shows a research focus in secondary and higher education, with one study in secondary education and two in higher education, totaling three studies. Lastly, Mauritania is represented by a single study focused on primary education.

The yearly distribution of studies from various North African countries from 2011 to 2023 indicates that Morocco has the highest number of studies. Studies from Morocco are recorded in each year from 2012 through 2023, except 2013 and 2018, and there are multiple studies listed in several of those years. Algeria has studies appearing in the years 2021, 2022, and 2023. Tunisia has studies in 2019 and 2023. Libya was represented in 2013 and 2018, while Mauritania had a single study documented in 2017. There are also records of studies involving various Maghreb region countries in 2011 and 2023. The year 2023 shows the most substantial number of studies, with a noticeable concentration of research, followed by 2022 and 2020. Earlier years have fewer studies listed.

Table.1: Contextual Distribution

Country	Primary Education	Secondary Education	Higher Education	Including Higher Ed/Secondary Ed	Total
Tunisia	0	1	1	0	2
Morocco	1	10	12	4	27
Various Countries (including the Maghreb region)	1	0	1	0	2
Algeria	0	0	4	0	4
Libya	0	1	2	0	3
Mauritania	1	0	0	0	1
Total	3	12	20	4	39

Fig. 2: Studies Yearly Distributions

Research Question 2: On which research problems have researchers concentrated their efforts?

The review's findings show that research efforts have been varied across different educational levels, with a stronger focus on secondary and higher education. Research issues like language use, teachers' experiences, and students' perceptions are more prevalent in these educational settings, whereas primary education sees limited research attention, particularly in areas like students' and teachers' experiences. Policy implementation and ideology are also critical focus areas across the educational spectrum.

The issue of language use has been a significant focus in secondary and higher education, with one study in secondary and four in higher education. However, it has not been addressed in primary education. One study has explored Students' experiences in higher education, but there's no emphasis on this aspect in primary and secondary education. Teachers' experiences have received attention predominantly in secondary education, with four studies, followed by two studies in higher education. However, this issue is not explored in the context of primary education. Pedagogical practice is another research area, with two studies each in primary and higher education, yet it is not a focus in secondary education.

Students' perceptions have been a considerable area of focus, especially in higher education, with six studies, followed by two in secondary education and two studies that include both higher and secondary education. Teachers' perceptions have been the subject of research in secondary education and higher education with one study each, but this area is not explored in primary and higher education.

Policy implementation is another key research issue addressed at all educational levels: one study in primary, two in secondary, two in higher education, and one study encompassing both higher and secondary education. The topic of ideology has been explored with two studies, each in secondary and higher education, and one study covering both educational levels. However, it is not a focus in primary education.

Table 2: Research Issues and Education Level Distribution

Research Issue/ Education Level	Primary Education	Secondary Education	Higher Education	Higher and Secondary Education
Language use	0	1	4	0
Student's experiences	0	0	1	0
Teachers' experiences	0	4	2	0
Pedagogical practice	2	0	2	0
Students' perceptions	0	2	6	2
Teachers' perception	0	1	1	0
Policy implementation	1	2	2	1
Ideology	0	2	2	1
Total	3	12	20	4

Research Question 3: Which participants have been incorporated in the studies?

The findings present a comprehensive array of participants across the spectrum of educational research. The studies included many students at various levels, from primary to university education, educators from different fields, and individuals involved in educational policy-making and practice. University students formed a large part of the participant base, with several studies focusing on this demographic. For instance, Abdeljaoued (2023) involved 434 students, while Chakrani and Huang (2012) included 454 university students. University Master's students were specifically targeted in the research by Agrram (2020); and Hamzaoui (2021), with participant numbers of 325 and 42, respectively. Further dissecting the student population, Bouziane (2020) and Chakrani (2015) focused on language-specific cohorts, involving 1477 students and 464 students, respectively; the latter was segmented into those taught in French and Standard Arabic. Teachers, professors, and educational leaders were also significantly featured in the studies. Notably, science teachers were the focus of multiple studies by authors such as Anaam (2022), Ben Hammou and Kesbi (2023a), Tamtam et al. (2013), and others, accounting for a range of 6 to 18 participants. Additionally, R'boul and Belhiah (2023) looked at the experiences of 25 EFL High School Teachers. At the higher education level, 55 Professors of Economics were examined in the study by Nadri and Haoucha (2020), while R'boul (2022) considered the perspectives of 24 university professors. The findings also included responses and data from broader educational

perspectives, as Van Pinxteren (2023) collected data from 120 countries. Smaller, focused groups were also part of the findings, providing in-depth insights into specific experiences and perceptions within the education system. This included a mix of students and teachers in smaller numbers, as seen in studies by Asker and Martin-Jones (2013) and Badwan (2019), the latter including 12 language policy influencers. Feedback in the form of comments was another dimension explored, with Bouziane and Saoudi (2021) analyzing 2,018 comments. Additionally, the research incorporated specific participant groups, such as high school students, undergraduate and master's level students, language teachers, and educational professionals, all contributing to a rich tapestry of research participants. Zakhir (2023) notably included a wide-reaching participant group of 445 parents, teachers, and students.

Research Question 4: Which research methodologies have been utilized by researchers?

The findings show a diverse methodology, with a notable emphasis on qualitative research approaches in 25 studies, constituting most of the studies primarily utilizing interviews, questionnaires, group discussions, content analysis, and observations. Quantitative methods were also represented, though to a lesser extent, in 8 studies. These included surveys, integrative data analysis, matched-guise tests, and various forms of questionnaires. Additionally, several studies employed mixed methods with 6 studies integrating surveys, observations, questionnaires, and interviews, indicating a blend of qualitative and quantitative approaches

Fig. 3: Frequency of Statistical Analysis Methods

Fig. 4: Research Design Distribution

Research Question 5: What are the reported outcomes and recommendations?

The extensive body of research in the scoping review offers a detailed exploration of the use and perception of different languages in educational settings across the Maghreb region, focusing primarily on Morocco, Libya, Tunisia, and Algeria. Collectively, these studies present a multifaceted view of how language policies and practices in education impact students, teachers, and broader societal dynamics.

In Tunisia, Abdeljaoued (2023) highlights that students view EMI positively, especially regarding career prospects. However, they also note a lack of proficiency in English among their content teachers, indicating a gap between policy aspirations and practical implementation. Badwan (2019) furthers this discussion by pointing out the challenges in

Tunisian higher education arising from the absence of formal language policies, including inconsistencies and potential social inequalities.

Morocco presents a complex picture of language use in education. Agrram (2020) finds that Moroccan students show a more receptive English vocabulary than those instructed in French compared to Arabic. This is complemented by Anaam's (2022) and Ben Hammou and Kesbi's (2023b) observations that secondary education teachers in Morocco feel the need for specialized EMI training, as many lack proficiency in English. Bouibhirne (2019) reports that Moroccan students struggle with language issues in French-taught courses, indicating a need for standardized resources and improved teaching methods. Chakrani and Huang (2012) highlight a preference among Moroccan students for French and English, particularly in science and technology education, which impacts local languages. Belhiah (2020); and Nadri and Haoucha (2020) note that Moroccan university students and professors acknowledge the benefits and challenges of EMI, emphasizing the need for improved pedagogical approaches. In a broader context, van Pinxteren (2023) contrasts this with the higher quality and student participation observed in educational systems using native languages instead of colonial ones.

According to Hamzaoui (2021), Algerian students value English for its job prospects and socio-economic benefits, preferring it over French. However, Alkhateeb and Bouherar (2022) criticize Algerian higher education institutions for neglecting linguistic sustainability, impacting language identity and learning.

Furthermore, the studies show that educational policies and cultural and societal factors influence regional language dynamics. For example, Zakhir and O'Brien (2019) observe that while students prefer French for formal education in Morocco, Moroccan Arabic is seen as practical in informal settings. Adriosh and Razi (2019) find in Libya that teachers and students positively view teaching in languages between Arabic and English for various pedagogical purposes. Tamtam et al. (2013) discuss the implications of using English and Arabic as instructional languages in Libyan universities, showing a mutual understanding that students prefer and find Arabic more accessible but recognize its limitations in enhancing job opportunities. Benzehaf (2021) notes that Moroccan university students view multilingualism positively, experiencing identity shifts due to it. These dynamics are further complicated by the influence of new media in Morocco, as Zakhir (2018) reports, elevating Moroccan Arabic from an oral to a written form, yet existing language ideologies constrain its educational use.

Recommendations from the Studies

A primary theme that emerges is the emphasis on language proficiency, particularly in English. Abdeljaoued (2023), Agrram (2020), Anaam (2022), and Ben Hammou & Kesbi (2021) underscore the critical importance of English proficiency, not only for students but also for teachers, especially in scientific subjects. This proficiency is seen as a cornerstone for effective EMI. The significance of English is reinforced by Maraf and Osam (2022), who argue for its integration due to its growing societal role.

Another central theme is teacher development and support. This is highlighted by Ben Hammou and Kesbi (2023a), Nadri and Haoucha (2020), and Ouarnik (2023), who advocate for comprehensive professional development and improved instructional strategies. This includes training in criterion-based assessment methods (Noyau, 2011) and adopting critical pedagogical approaches (R'boul & Belhiah, 2023). The development of metalinguistic skills, as suggested by Noyau (2017), and addressing issues like native-speakerism in English Language Teaching practices (Mourchid M et al., 2022) are also emphasized.

The role of language policy forms another significant recommendation theme. Studies by Bouibhirne (2019), Chakrani and Huang (2012), Belhiah (2020), Van Pinxteren (2023), and others focus on the importance of multilingualism and the inclusion of local languages in the educational system. This is echoed in recommendations for a balanced approach to language policy, recognizing the importance of Standard Arabic, French, and local dialects (Chakrani, 2020; Zakhir and O'Brien (2017); Yearous, 2012). In this light, the studies recommend enhancing the social status of local languages in

Morocco's education system, recognizing its cultural heritage (Zakhir, 2023), and affirming the positioning of Arabic as a language of scientific knowledge while accommodating linguistic diversity. The need for flexible and inclusive language policies, particularly in Libyan and Tunisian education systems, is also discussed (Asker & Martin-Jones, 2013; Badwan, 2019; Tamtam, 2013).

A detailed approach to language teaching is suggested, where Moroccan Arabic is seen as a transitional tool in learning Standard Arabic (Zakhir & O'Brien, 2019). The practicality of classroom code-switching, facilitating understanding while not interrupting target language acquisition, is highlighted by Adriosh and Razi. (2019). Further, there is a recommendation for research on using Moroccan Arabic in social media among teenagers (Zakhir, 2018).

Cultural aspects and intercultural dynamics in language learning and higher education are also significant. The studies underscore the need for equitable distribution of professional development resources and a deeper understanding of language ideologies in teaching practices (Smail, 2017). The importance of embracing multilingualism, fostering creativity, and constructing plural identities in classrooms is stressed (Benzehaf, 2021). In this context, ecological interventions and holistic, student-oriented language planning are advocated (Alkhateeb & Bouherar, 2022).

Conclusions and Suggestions for Future Research

This scoping review, encompassing 39 empirical studies, offers a detailed insight into language instruction within the Maghreb region. Various conclusions can be drawn from the findings of this review. A key finding is the uneven geographical distribution of these studies, with Morocco, especially in its secondary and higher education sectors, being the focal point. In contrast, Tunisia, Libya, and Mauritania have seen scant research, indicating a potential area for future exploration. These studies predominantly focus on language use, the experiences of teachers and students, pedagogical practices, and policy implementation. The emphasis on language use and teachers' experiences in secondary and higher education underscores the unique challenges at these educational levels.

Methodologically, the studies exhibit a preference for qualitative approaches involving a diverse range of participants, from students to policy-makers. This diversity provides a comprehensive understanding of the language instruction landscape in the Maghreb region. The outcomes and recommendations from these studies highlight significant issues, including the disconnect between policy and practice, challenges in adopting EML, and the necessity for specialized teacher training in multilingual contexts.

However, several research gaps are evident. There's an imbalance in the focus across educational levels and countries within the region, with research concentrated on secondary and higher education, Tunisia and Libya present opportunities for expanding into primary education. Conversely, Mauritania, focusing on primary education, could benefit from research in higher educational sectors. Comparative studies between countries like Morocco and the less-researched Mauritania could yield insights into the efficacy of different educational policies and practices.

Notably, there is a lack of studies in primary education, particularly concerning language use, which is well-covered in higher educational stages. While student experiences are examined in higher education, this aspect is significantly under-researched at primary and secondary levels. Similarly, teachers' experiences, predominantly focused on secondary education, lack comparable attention in primary education. Though studied in primary and higher education, pedagogical practices need more focus in secondary education. Although thoroughly explored in higher and secondary education, the perceptions of students and teachers are less attended to in primary education.

Additionally, while addressed across various educational levels, policy implementation and ideology are underexplored in primary education. Future research should aim for a balanced approach encompassing all educational levels. This involves expanding the scope of focus on language use, students' and teachers' experiences, pedagogical practices, perceptions, and policy implementation in primary education.

The prevalent use of qualitative methods, like interviews, questionnaires, and observations, indicates their effectiveness in offering in-depth perspectives. However, there is a need for more quantitative methods to provide statistical

validation and generalizability. The infrequent use of mixed methods, which integrate both qualitative and quantitative approaches, is seen as highly valuable, suggesting a potential area for methodological expansion in future research.

Author Contribution Statement

The authors confirm sole responsibility for the following: study conception and design, data collection, analysis and interpretation of results, and manuscript preparation.

Financial Support

This research received no specific grant from any funding agency, commercial or not-for-profit sectors.

Declaration of Interest

None.

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Appendix A

Manually Searched Journals

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1. Applied Linguistics
 2. Al-'Arabiyya: A Journal
 3. Arab World English Journal
 4. English Studies at NBU: A Journal
 5. Bilingualism: Language and Cognition
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6. Linguistic Approaches to Bilingualism
7. International Journal of Bilingualism
8. International Journal of Bilingual Education and Bilingualism
9. Multilingual: Journal of Cross-Cultural and Interlanguage Communication
10. Journal of Multilingual and Multicultural Development
11. International Multilingual Research Journal
12. International Journal of Multilingualism
13. Open Edition Journals
14. Afak for Sciences Journal
15. Frontiers in Psychology
16. International Journal of Language and Literary Studies
17. Studies in Second Language Learning and Teaching
18. International Journal of Educational Development
19. World Englishes: MENA - World Englishes in the Middle East and North Africa
20. TESOL Quarterly: English Language Development in Tunisia
21. Language and Education
22. Issues in Language Planning

Appendix B
Studies Findings in the Maghreb Region

Authors	Themes	Educational Level	Country	Participants	Methodology	Study Objective
Abdeljaoued (2023)	Student perceptions/classroom interaction	Higher Education	Tunisia	434 students	Mixed: surveys, classroom observation	Provides a comprehensive examination of Tunisian university students' attitudes towards EMI.
Adriosh and Razi (2019)	Student Experiences/Language Use	Higher Education	Libya	24 students	Qualitative: observation and interviews	Investigates how EFL teachers code-switch to facilitate teaching/learning process
Agram (2020)	language use	Higher Education	Morocco	325 University Master's Students	Quantitative: Surveys	Explores how the choice of instructional languages impacts the receptive vocabulary size among Moroccan students learning English as a Foreign Language (EFL).
Alkhateeb and Bouherar (2022)	Students' perceptions	Higher Education	Algeria	30 students	Mixed: Q methodology/group discussion/interviews	Evaluates if higher education institutions in the Arab world have adopted linguistic sustainability approaches.

Anaam (2022)	Teachers' experiences	Secondary Education	Morocco	6 Science Teachers	Qualitative: interviews	Explores the experiences and viewpoints of math and science teachers in Moroccan public secondary schools regarding their training for using EMI.
Asker and Martin-Jones (2013)	Teacher perception	Secondary Education	Libya	2 student participants and 2 teachers	Qualitative: interviews, observations	Examines how beliefs and ideologies regarding 'suitable' language use are manifested and perpetuated in multilingual classroom interactions and code-switching practices during local English lessons.
Badwan (2019)	Policy implementation /ideology	Secondary Education	Tunisia	12 Language Policy Influencers	Qualitative: interviews	Examines how structural elements and individual choices interact within the framework of language policies in Tunisian higher education,
Belhiah (2020)	Student perceptions/language use	Higher Education	Morocco	286 Students	Qualitative: interviews and focus groups.	Highlights the increasing prevalence of English in Morocco by exploring the reasons behind university students' choice of English as their major, delving into their underlying motivations for this decision.
Ben Hammou and Kesbi (2020)	Teacher experiences	Secondary Education	Morocco	15 Science Teachers	Qualitative: interviews	Investigates the perspectives of Moroccan physics teachers on employing English and French as languages of instruction in secondary schools.
Ben Hammou and Kesbi (2022)	Students' perceptions	Higher Education	Morocco	17 science students	Qualitative: interviews	Focuses on the attitudes of Moroccan graduate students towards EMI in Moroccan higher education, particularly in science universities.
Ben Hammou and Kesbi (2023a)	Teachers' experiences	Secondary Education	Morocco	18 Science Teachers	Qualitative: interviews	Explores the perceptions and experiences of Moroccan secondary school science teachers regarding the implementation and effects of a small-scale EMI program.

Ben Hammou and Kesbi (2023b)	Language use/Teacher perception	Secondary Education	Morocco	15 Science Teachers	Qualitative: interviews	Focuses on science teachers' perceptions of these policies, especially how the policy of alternating languages is being implemented at the secondary school level.
Benzehaf (2021)	Students' perceptions	Higher Education	Morocco	32 students	Qualitative: interviews, group discussions	Examines how Moroccan university English students perceive multilingualism and its impact on their identity construction.
Bouibhime (2019)	Pedagogical practice/student experiences	Higher Education	Morocco	62 Students	Qualitative: interviews	Investigate the appropriateness and effectiveness of the current French language instruction in professional bachelor's degree programs in Morocco.
Bouziane (2020)	Student Perceptions /Language Use	Higher Education/ Secondary Education	Morocco	1477 students	Quantitative: surveys	Investigates the attitudes of Moroccan students towards the most widely used languages in Morocco (Standard Arabic, Moroccan Arabic, Amazigh, French, and English) and to identify factors influencing these attitudes.
Bouziane and Saoudi (2021)	Language Use	Higher Education	Morocco	2,018 comments	Qualitative: content analysis	Investigates attitudes towards adopting English as a first foreign language in Morocco, and how these attitudes relate to other languages used in the country.
Chakrani (2015)	Language use and policy implementation	Higher Education	Morocco	464 students	Quantitative: questionnaires	Investigate how the language of instruction influences students' overt language attitudes
Chakrani (2020)	Policy Implementation/Student Perceptions	Higher Education/ Secondary Education	Morocco	23 Students	Quantitative: matched-guise test	Investigates language attitudes towards Standard Arabic (SA) and French in Morocco to ascertain whether they are indeed aligned, as traditionally presumed, based on the dimensions of status and solidarity.

Chakrani and Huang (2012)	Ideology/language use	Higher Education	Morocco	454 University Students	Qualitative: questionnaires	Examines the explicit language attitudes and behaviors of Moroccan university students taught in French, focusing on the link between their linguistic practices and attitudes.
Elyazale (2019)	Language use/ Student perceptions	Higher Education	Morocco	454 students	Quantitative: questionnaires	Examines the attitudes of university students towards English and English for Specific Purposes learning in the Moroccan context, especially focusing on the undergraduate economy and Master economy and law students.
Hamzaoui (2021)	Student perceptions	Higher Education	Algeria	42 University Master's Students	Mixed: questionnaires, interview	Examines students' preferences for the language used in instruction and their attitudes toward instruction entirely conducted in English.
Maraf and Osam (2022)	Policy Implementation/ Student perception	Higher Education	Algeria	20 students	Qualitative: Observations, content analysis, interviews	Provides an insight into foreign language policy endeavor in Algeria and understand the influence of the Smile Revolution on the growing use of English in Algeria and the resultant government policy decisions.
Mourchid et al. (2023)	Student Perceptions/Language Use	Higher Education/ Secondary Education	Morocco	119 participants (76 Moroccan EFL students, and 43 Moroccan EFL teachers)	Mixed: questionnaires	Discusses native-speakerism in English language teaching, explores Moroccan EFL students' attitudes towards native and non-native English-speaking teachers, and measures Moroccan EFL teachers' self-perceptions regarding their proficiency and comfort in teaching.
Nadri and Haoucha (2020)	Teacher experiences/ policy implementation	Higher Education	Morocco	55 Professors of Economics	Qualitative: questionnaires	Explores the potential for implementing EMI in Moroccan higher education institutions, assessing the feasibility and implications of this change.
Noyau (2011)	Pedagogical practice	Primary Education	Various Countries	60 Students	Qualitative: content analysis	Explores how differences between educational curricula and assessment practices impact the development of bilingual abilities in primary school students.

Noyau (2017)	Pedagogical practice/student experiences:	Primary Education	Mauritania	Students/teachers	Qualitative: Observations, interviews	Analyze the difficulties Mauritanian students encounter in accessing written French as their second language of schooling.
Ouarnik (2023)	Teacher experiences	Higher Education	Algeria	10 Teachers	Qualitative: interviews	Examines the views of Algerian higher education instructors on the use of EMI within their educational establishments.
R'boul (2022)	Language use/teacher experiences	Higher Education	Morocco	24 University Professors	Qualitative: group discussions	Delves into the reasons, processes, and consequences of implementing English as the language of instruction in Moroccan educational settings.
R'boul (2022)	Ideology	Higher Education	Morocco	32 participants (28 undergraduate and master students, and 4 professors)	Qualitative: focus group discussions, interviews, and classroom observations.	Examines university students' and professors' perspectives and engagements with the English language in Morocco.
R'boul and Belhiah (2023)	Ideology/teacher perception	Secondary Education	Morocco	25 EFL High School Teachers	Qualitative: interviews	Explores the effects of neo-nationalism on English language teaching and the perceptions of teachers in Morocco, particularly in the context of the country's sociolinguistic dynamics and national identity.
R'boul et al. (2023)	Language use/student perceptions	Secondary Education	Morocco	20 students	Qualitative: interviews	Aims to analyze how Moroccan students' complex linguistic identities and perspectives interact with the country's diverse language landscape.
Smail (2017)	Teacher Experiences/Ideology	Secondary Education	Morocco	20 language teachers (9 Arabic, 11 English).	Qualitative: Observations, interviews	Examines how Moroccan language teachers perceive good teaching practice, focusing on learner-centered education, and explore the impact of language pedagogies influenced by politics and resource disparities.
Tamtam et al. (2013)	Teacher Perception	Higher Education	Libya	5 teachers	Qualitative	Investigate teaching staff views on language of instruction impact on the quality of education in two Libyan universities.

Van Pinxteren (2023)	Language use/pedagogical practice	Higher Education	Various Countries	Data from 120 countries	Quantitative: integrative data analysis	Introduces a systems-oriented method for investigating how the medium of instruction affects student performance.
Yearous (2012)	Student perceptions	Secondary Education	Morocco	50 High School Students	Mixed: questionnaires, interviews	Examines how Arabization policies affect high school students in Morocco, its impact, and outcomes.
Zakhir (2018)	Ideology	Secondary Education	Morocco	63 students/6 teachers	Mixed: questionnaires,	Investigates the impact of new media on language use in Moroccan society and education.
Zakhir (2023)	Policy Implementation/Teacher Perceptions	Primary Education	Morocco	445 participants, (143 parents, 31 Amazigh teachers, and 271 students)	Mixed: questionnaires, interviews, tests	Investigates the barriers to implementing Amazigh in primary schools and its effects on students' academic achievement.
Zakhir and O'Brien (2017)	Policy implementation	Secondary Education	Morocco	199 Respondents (136 Students, and 63 teachers)	Qualitative: questionnaires	Clarifies the disparity between the official policy of Arabization, which involves the adoption and use of Standard Arabic, and the actual implementation of this policy in science classrooms.
Zakhir and O'Brien (2019)	Ideology/Language Use/Student Perceptions/Language Use	Higher Education/ Secondary Education	Morocco	200 participants (172 students and 28 teachers)	Mixed: questionnaires	Examines the status of Moroccan Arabic in education and the different ideologies around it.

